

About the Dark-room Problem Raised by The Free Energy Principle

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Abstract

The theoretical dark-room problem raised by the free energy principle sheds light on the very concrete problem of ideologies that plague humanity.

Let us recall, first, that the free energy principle entails that we live in the world of our conception of the world. Second, it identifies two ways of minimizing surprise: modifying the model to eliminate the surprise revealed by action, or modifying the environment so that it conforms to the model.

An ideology is a hypostatized conception of the world, a model, embodied by a community which, over several generations and through the language performativity, has established a common world, partly imaginary, by invisibilizing everything that did not conform to its model. An ideological community operates at the macro-level of humanity's econiche with the aim of extending itself to the rest of the world.

Theoretically, the alternative strategy—modifying the model—may seem superior. In practice, however, it is not, so long as the model remains confined to the micro-level of the agent. This is the darkroom dual problem: the problem of the powerless spectator. It is a scale problem which, at this point, may seem practically insurmountable.

The configuration of humanity's econiche, saturated with ideologies, is path dependent. I will argue that its trajectory has been and will continue to be strongly shaped by two Darwinian invariants: the propensity for control and the phenotypic diversity of our species.

About the Dark-room Problem Raised by The Free Energy Principle

“ The opposition of thinking and acting, which, depriving thought of reality and action of sense, makes both meaningless. ”

Hannah Arendt

The dark-room problem may be stated as follows: does the free energy principle's imperative to minimize surprise entail the existence of a type of model whose actions generate no prediction errors with respect to the environment it models?

In the paper *Free-Energy Minimization and The Dark-Room Problem*, Andy Clark (the philosopher), Christopher Thornton (the theorist) and Karl Friston (the physicist) discuss this problem. Toward the end of their discussion, the philosopher concludes that:

«The dark-room scenario cannot then obtain unless staying in the dark room is itself the way to minimize surprise relative to the expectations implicitly defined by that entire, and importantly niche-reflecting, model. That means that for creatures like us, the dark room is simply not an attractor.»

However, not only do ideologies constitute dark-room-type constructions, but there also exists another kind of niche construction that may be understood as a dark room dual.

Let us recall two major explanatory strengths of the free energy principle: the relation between the hierarchical levels of Markov blankets, and the close relation between a model and the action it generates, which are in a way the two sides of the same coin. This implies that the value of a model is up to the effectiveness of the action it generates. My model may accurately represent my environment, but if it does not enable me to act, it is utterly worthless.

Here, the concept of ideology refers to a kind of malevolent lie transposed onto the collective scale, onto the scale of conception of the world, and onto the scale of History. It is a dogmatic misconception of the world composed of false beliefs and erroneous, hypostatized theories that generate a dark-room within which the community embodying the ideology encloses itself. Such a community seeks to impose itself upon the rest of the world and tends toward totalitarianism.

Incidentally, a parallel between dark-rooms and Plato's cave comes to mind.

With the exception of scientism, an ideology always has a clearly identified enemy: a despised and dehumanized “them”. In this way, it assumes — albeit in an imaginary way — the unimaginary form of the “us against them” of our more or less distant ancestors. Moreover, by competing to configure the world each in its own way, ideologies form a polarizing dynamic system that, fueled by their mutual contempt, could rapidly degenerate. Finally, even though they compete against one another, together they reinforce dogmatism.

The problem with the above quotation revolves around the notion of “ creatures like us ” because the attractors to which I refer are constructed by agents in order to trap other agents within ideological dark-rooms. Because the action that shapes our world unfolds at two levels. Indeed, our species has constructed above the concrete (physical) foundation of our world, an abstract layer through the intersubjectivity of language and the conceptual materials it provides. Structured by an entanglement of institutions, this abstract layer is path dependent (that is, its configuration depends on the cumulative effects of the past actions of all agents). Its orientation is fundamentally Darwinian, in the sense that its transformation is governed by the Darwinian propensity for control and by the phenotypic diversity of our species. ^{1, 2}

Darwinian Orientation of the Path on Which the Configuration of our World Depends

“The primary dynamic that has driven and is currently driving human evolution is competition with other people and groups of other people for resource control, including control of the behavior of other people.”

Geary

DARWINIAN PROPENSITY FOR CONTROL

“...the unifying theme is that individuals of all species have evolved to attempt to organize their world in ways that eliminate predatory risks (e.g. evasion behaviors) and enhance survival and reproductive options, or at least to do so in ways that facilitated these outcomes during the species’ evolutionary history. My shorthand for these behavioral biases is a motivation to control. [...]

Human behavior, and at an abstract level the behavior of all species, can thus be conceptualized in terms of an evolved motivation to control. [...]

The primary dynamic that has driven and is currently driving human evolution is competition with other people and groups of other people for resource control, including control of the behavior of other people. [...]

[H]umans are ecologically dominant, and once this was achieved, there was an important shift such that the competing interests of other people and coalitions of other people became, and remain, the central pressure that influences human evolution.

From this perspective, natural selection remains a ‘struggle for existence’ but becomes primarily a struggle with other human beings for control of the resources that support life and allow one to reproduce. ”

Geary

The propensity for control has profoundly contributed to shaping the intersubjective layer of our ecological niche. In particular because the best way to control other individuals is to control

¹ Note that the abstract ontology of the upper layer of our econiche can be solidly founded.

² Language is infinitely more performative than Austin initially theorized if we conceive that the upper layer of our econiche, the abstract intersubjective world, was constructed with materials provided by language.

their beliefs unbeknownst to them, by removing from their cultural environment options they might otherwise have chosen. This is what ideologies do.

The question that begs to be asked is: who is in control within an ideological sub-econiche? However, this is not quite the right wording, because History is partly in control. This kind of control from beyond the grave requires a community that is captive to a closed cultural environment, a dark-room, conceptually impoverished so that the dogmas are indubitable.

“ Under the free-energy principle, the agent will become an optimal (if approximate) model of its environment [...]

Avoiding surprises means that one has to model and anticipate a changing and itinerant world. This implies that the models used to quantify surprise must themselves embody itinerant wandering through cognitive³ states.” [Friston, Thornton, Clark](#)

Ideological models also incorporate a form of itinerant wandering, but one that unfolds at the scales of History and the econiche. Non-ideological itinerant wandering seeks to correct the surprise revealed by action, “in real time.” It is, in a sense, synchronous. Ideological wandering, by contrast, occurs only when the dogmatic misconception of the world collapses, undermined by an accumulation of factual disconfirmations that can no longer be ignored, since the performativity of lies are not unlimited.

We can take as an example the far left which, in order to survive, had to morph from Marxism into identitarianism.

COGNITIVE DIVERSIFICATION OF OUR DISTANT ANCESTORS

“My argument is that the foci of control-related behavioral biases and the supporting brain, perceptual, cognitive, and affective systems are three general forms of resource: social, biological, and physical. The corresponding competencies are captured by the domains of folk psychology (...), folk biology (...), and folk physics (...). When applied to humans, these domains refer to an inherent and intuitive understanding of other people (folk psychology), other species (folk biology), and the physical world (folk physics). When meshed with ecological dominance and a struggle with other people to control these ecologies, the result is an evolutionary arms race. An arms race refers to the evolutionary change that results from the competing interests of individuals, within or between species, as they attempt to achieve competitive advantage.”

[Geary](#)

The phenotypic diversity of species is a fundamental key to evolution allowing, for instance, a species to avoid extinction by discovering and occupying new niches.

From the concept of phenotypic diversity,⁴ we can induce the concept of models diversity. At the perceptual level, we have the example of dichromatism which gives the advantage of perceiving imperceptible things to a trichromatic agent. Dichromatism may give an advantage

³ I replaced “sensory” with “cognitive”.

⁴ Also called statistical distribution of phenotypes.

for hunting as well as for survival, when, for instance, a dichromatic agent is threatened by an ambush enemy.

Thus, in certain econiches, a community that has both dichromatic and trichromatic agents is less likely to become extinct than one that has trichromatic agents only. In short, a species, or a community, may minimize surprise by means of an adaptative diversification of its phenotype.

At the level of the abstract layer, diversity takes the form of the diversity of conceptions of the world. Believe or not believe in supernatural forces, for instance. It is important to keep in mind that our conception of the world does not serve only to describe the external world so that we may act within it; it also serves to act upon our affective consciousness, the primary level of our consciousness (Solms). For instance, believing in heaven after death can be anxiolytic.

A conception of the world has only one existence criterion, it must be embodied by at least one agent. Otherwise, it simply does not exist.

As I mentioned above, one of the great strengths of the free energy principle is that it schematizes the hierarchical structure of the living world. Thus, at the macro level above us lies our ecological niche, composed of different “territories” — sub-econiches — occupied, for instance, by different ideologies. Just as the existence criterion of a conception of the world is to be embodied by an agent, the existence criterion of an ideology is to be embodied by a community acting at the level of the econiche with the aim of imposing itself upon the rest of the world.

According to the free energy principle, there are two complementary ways of minimizing surprise: modifying the environment and modifying the model. But at the level of the intersubjective layer, these two ways seem to become mutually exclusive survival strategies: either shaping (controlling) the sub-econiche by hypostaticizing its theories, as well as invisibilizing whatever does not accord with the model, as ideological communities do, or seeking to read the world as it is — that is, seeking out what does not accord with the model in order to amend it accordingly and thereby act more effectively.

Theoretically, these are options within our space of freedom, but in practice, History — the path shaped by the propensity for control, upon which the sub-econiche depends — has too often eliminated the second option.

When I first became interested in the free energy principle, I assumed that the *raison d'être* of the conscious part of our internal model was to model reality as it truly is, but that is not the case. Its *raison d'être* is our survival through action. Thus, our model dictates what we must do. Our model determines our actions. Yet for many species, including our own, survival depends on belonging to a community. And for human beings, such belonging often requires adopting as one's own what the community regards as truth. As a result, modeling reality as it is constitutes only one survival strategy, and not necessarily the best one.

The fundamental problem concealed beneath all this is not the problem of truth, it is the problem of freedom. The problem of freedom does not appear in lower hierarchical layers of Markov blankets, nor even at the level of perception. Dichromatism is not an option. Intentional

freedom emerges at the cognitive level. Diversity of beliefs and conceptions of the world proves it. For instance, we have the option of lying to others, to deceive them, as well as lying to ourselves, either to feel better or because it serves our interests. Lying and deceiving are options generated by our models. All our actions are generated by our models.

This begs the question: what brings somebody to inhabit an ideological dark-room?

The short answer is that the model is good enough, and that the cost of developing one's own model depends on one's own phenotype,⁵ whereas this cost is practically zero since the model is not developed but inherited. Or simply because one is born into it, or for affective gain, or for pragmatic reasons.

What leads somebody to remain in it?

There is no satisfactory short answer. We must elaborate.

Let's begin by recalling that the free energy principle entails that, even though physically, we all live in the same physical world, mentally, we live in the world built with the tools that our conception of the world provides us. This implies that, mentally, we inhabit divergent worlds insofar as our conceptions of the world diverge.

Human Freedom and Its Link With Consciousness⁶

Our freedom and our consciousness, which are constitutive of our internal model, coexist and they both depend on our body and our health.

1. Our conception of freedom conditions our freedom, because if we misunderstand freedom, we cannot know to what extent we are free. And if we don't know to what extent we are not free, freeing ourselves cannot be an option.

2. The Concept of Consciousness

Our consciousness can be seen as a product of natural selection, just like our legs and our eyes. Like all the other faculties we have inherited, it evolved because it conferred an adaptive advantage on our distant ancestors. However, there is an important distinction. Our consciousness — that is, the faculty that allows us to be conscious — must be distinguished from being conscious of what we are conscious of, just as we distinguish our legs from walking.

Our consciousness allows us to be conscious of what we are conscious of, but it merely makes this possible. This implies that being conscious is neither necessarily effortless nor automatic. Because we are often mistaken and misled.

Moreover, unlike our legs and our eyes, our consciousness is neither tangible nor material, even though its existence depends on our brain and body. So if it is immaterial and

⁵ Consider John von Neumann's phenotype, for instance.

⁶ This part has been reworked from: [*Preventing a Civilizational Collapse With The Help of The Free Energy Principle*](#)

intangible, what could it possibly be made of?
It can be shown that it is an abstract entity.

3. To apprehend the relation between our freedom and our consciousness, we will distinguish the set of options that we could choose now, from the decision-maker who chooses.

3.1. In order to highlight the fact that this set has a structure, we will call it our freedom space. The decision-maker and the freedom space are not really distinct. We distinguish them abstractly to help us conceptualize our freedom and the relation between our freedom and our consciousness.

4. Our freedom space depends, among other things, on our physical, cultural, and conceptual environment.

4.1. Our freedom space depends not only on the options offered to us by our environment, it also depends on our knowledge of those options, the acquisition of which is under the charge of our consciousness.

5. Our freedom space is path dependent. It can shrink or, on the contrary, expand, depending on the options we choose.

6. One of the conditions of our freedom is the absence of constraints (this is a delicate point). Distinguishing between the decision-maker and the freedom space allows us to distinguish different types of constraints.

6.1. Those of which we are aware: we would like to choose an option, but a manifest coercive force prevents us from doing so, e.g., we are in jail.

6.2. Constraints that we chose, e.g., those imposed by the decision to become a parent.

6.3. Institutional constraints, e.g., paying a fine.

6.4. And most importantly, constraints of which we cannot be aware, because options we might have chosen have, unbeknownst to us, been removed from our environment. Namely, from our cultural and conceptual environments whose configuration has been strongly conditioned by the propensity for control. In such cases, when the constraints are invisible, we do not know that we are not free.

7. Our conceptual tools.

7.1. Since our conceptual tools are neither true nor false, but rather more or less adapted to the tasks we want them to perform, they are not on the same level as our beliefs. This gives us a glimpse of the structure of our freedom space.

7.2. It is with our conceptual tools that we read the world.

7.3. With very few exceptions, our conceptual tools come directly from our conceptual environment.

7.4. Among all our conceptual tools, our liberating conceptual tools that enable us to expose the lies upon which dark-rooms are erected are indispensable to our freedom.

This completes the answer to our second question. Those trapped within an ideological dark-room do not merely inhabit the world of their misconception of the world; they inhabit the common world they collectively embody.

Dark-Room's Dual

The notion of duality is used here to evoke the relation between the two sides of the same coin: model, on the one hand, action, on the other hand.

“ the FEP is a non-substantive principle that can be applied to any biological system in general (much like Hamilton's principle of least action).” [Ramstead](#)

An ideological conception of the world is good enough insofar as it enables to stay alive. However, if we add to the equation the possibility of our species' extinction in order to try to avoid it, or if we consider the suffering caused by human beings in order to try to reduce it (think of the suffering caused by wars), then the equation becomes substantive.

Intuitively, for an intellectual, the non-ideological strategy of seeking discrepancies between our model and reality seems preferable to the ideological strategy of invisibilizing them. Except that this is not necessarily the case, because the value of a model is assessed through the action it generates.

Indeed, the model is only one part of the equation, and not even the most important part. Non-ideological models may strive to describe the world as it is, but those who adopt them are doomed to be supplanted by ideologies if they fail to find a way to act in concert at the level of the econiche, so as to counter ideological blindness.

To get out of this dark-room's dual, if we want to act substantially at the level of the econiche, we must organize ourselves, we must give ourselves an organization that will allow us to agree on a common model.⁷

References

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⁷ See: *Preventing a Civilizational Collapse With The Help of The Free Energy Principle*.